

Effect of Smoking on Hematological Parameters in Patients with Polycythemia and Comparing Them with Healthy People

Atheer Shehab Ahmed

The General Directorate for Education of Diyala, Baqubah32001, Iraq

Ahmed Khalid Abdullah

Department of Physiology, College of Medicine, University of Diyala, Baqubah32001, Iraq

Ahmed Taher Mahmood

The General Directorate for Education of Diyala, Baqubah32001, Iraq

Abstract

The aim of this study is to Measure the red and white blood cells and platelet counts (complete blood picture). in patients with polycythemia and comparing them with healthy people(control). 90 blood samples are collected from these patients (54 smokers, 36 nonsmokers) and they are compared with 40 blood samples of healthy persons within the age range of (18-79 years). A Hematocrit (HCT) criterion of 52% is used in the study as a sickness criterion. Results of the statistical analysis show a significant increase ($p < 0.001$) in red blood cells, compared to the control group, there was a significant rise in the number of white blood cells ($p < 0.05$) and neutrophils, monocytes, and eosinophils ($p < 0.001$), but a significant fall in the number of lymphocytes and basophils ($p < 0.001$). The platelets count did not mirror any significant variations between the patients and control groups despite the increase in platelet numbers in persons with polycythemia group that are nonsmokers and a decrease in smokers. Notes from the above results The effect of smoking on blood serum show a significant increase in red blood cells, hematocrit, white blood cells, and that this increase appears clearly in smokers and non-smokers patients.

Introduction

Polycythaemia is when there are too many red blood cells in the blood. It usually happens to adults over fifty, but it can happen to anyone from 15 to 90 years old, and men are more likely than women to get it. If the number of white blood cells, platelets, and red blood cells goes up along with the number of red blood cells, this rise is real or main [1]. As for secondary polycythemia, it results due to the increased secretion of hormone regulating the production of red blood cells from the bone marrow as a result of a lack of oxygenation of tissues, and there are many reasons that lead to lack of oxygen in the blood, including living in the highlands, heart and respiratory diseases, smoking, and some cancerous diseases may cause this type as a result of secreting hormone regulating the production of red blood cells [2]. When there isn't enough blood plasma, there are more red blood cells but not as many white blood cells. This is called relative

polycythaemia and can happen from taking too many diuretic drugs or not drinking enough water [3]. To study this phenomenon from some aspects, the term hyperoxidation was used to measure oxidative damage at the cell, tissue, and organ level caused by active oxygen types. In normal conditions of the biological system, there is an equilibrium between the production of active oxygen species and their removal by antioxidant defense systems [4]. There are many sources of generating effective oxygen radicals, including internal as by-products of basic metabolic reactions such as energy production processes in mitochondria or detoxification reactions in the liver, including external environmental influences such as ionizing rays such as X-rays, exposure to sunlight for long periods, cigarette smoke, in addition to chemicals and heavy metals such as iron and copper, which enter into biochemical reactions within the body known as Fenton reactions and lead to the formation of free

More Information

How to cite this article: Ahmed AS, Abdullah AK, Mahmood AT. Effect of Smoking on Hematological Parameters in Patients with Polycythemia and Comparing Them with Healthy People. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(5):313-17.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(5).35

Keywords:

Smoking,
Polycythemia,
Hemoglobin,
Hyperoxidation.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

radicals. Free radicals in the body are an obstacle to good human health as they attack and destroy cells [5].

Methodology

The study included 90 male participants (aged 18-79 years) who visited the blood bank/health department in Diyala for the purpose of blood disposal. A separate criterion of 52% or higher blood concentration was adopted as the sole method for diagnosing the disease. This group was composed of patients with polycythemia. Within this group of polycythemia patients, they were divided into two subgroups based on smoking status: smokers (those who smoked more than 10 cigarettes per day) and non-smokers. Blood criteria in these two groups were compared to a healthy control group of 40 males (aged 19-51 years). Venous blood samples were collected from the mentioned subjects in the period 3-1 by 10 ml and 2.5 ml were placed in a tube containing (EDTA) Ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid for the purpose of performing the total blood counts (CBC) Complete blood counts with the Sysmex automatic counting device.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis is often used to analyze quantitative data, and provides methods for data description, simple inference for continuous and categorical data. The procedure involves the collection of data leading to test of the relationship between two statistical data sets. In this study all data are presented as frequency and percentage. We used SPSS (version 26) and the dependent t-test (two-tailed) and independent t-test (two-tailed) for variables that had a normally distributed distribution. We used the Mann-Whitney U test, the Wilcoxon test, and the Chi-square test for factors that did not have a normally distributed shape. $M < 0.05$ was thought to be statistically important.

Total blood count and blood parameters

The levels of blood parameters HB, WBC, RBC, HCT, MCV, MCH, (MCHC in the blood samples placed in the EDTA tube were measured using the automatic total counting device for blood analyzes (SYSMEX KX21N) as the said device consists of three main parts and depends on the use of two types of reagents in the analysis of the blood sample. The number of leukocytes was calculated by the part of (leukocytes) and using the Direct Current method. As for the measurement of the level of hemoglobin, it was carried out using the part of the Hb and using the non-cyanide hemoglobin method.

The working principle of the automatic counting device (Principle)

The principle of action is based on two methods of analyzing the sample blood sample.

Direct current detection method

The device instantly takes 50µl from the blood sample and puts it into the carrier's chamber. There is a small hole in the transducer chamber called an aperture. There are electrodes on both sides of the aperture from

which direct current runs. As the blood cells in the sample move through the hole, they change the direct current resistance between the electrodes. The size of the blood cells can be measured by the electric pulses that are caused by this change in direct current resistance. Blood cells are counted and a statistical histogram showing the sizes of blood cells is included by determining the size of electrical impulses. A statistical histogram of the remaining various analysis data is also included [6].

Measurement of blood hemoglobin concentration

The analysis of blood hemoglobin using automated methods such as the Cyanmethemoglobin or Oxyhemoglobin method is still considered one of the main approaches. The Cyanmethemoglobin method was internationally standardized in 1966 by the International Committee for Standardization in Hematology. However, this method has very low conversion rates for hemoglobin and is not suitable for multiple automated sample analyses. Additionally, the method itself uses a compound detector called Cyanide, which is a toxic substance requiring waste treatment. Its use necessitates complex waste management procedures and has harmful effects on the environment. Therefore, this method is currently not suitable. Conversely, the Oxyhemoglobin method is characterized by its speed in the conversion rate of hemoglobin. As hemoglobin turns instantaneously into Oxyhemoglobin and this method does not contain a toxic substance, but the Oxyhemo method is unable to convert methemoglobin into Oxyhemoglobin. Thus, the blood containing large amounts of methemoglobin will lead to low results despite the absence of health problems in humans [6].

Ethical approval

The study was okay with the human ethics committee of Diyala's blood bank and health department. Those who agreed to take part in the study were told about it and asked to sign a form. The patient was also told that no one else would see his details.

Results and Discussion

The number of red blood cells in non-smoking and smoking polycythaemia patients was significantly higher than in healthy people ($P = 0.001$) (Table 1). They reached 5.21 ± 0.075 (6.00 ± 0.064) and $5.95 \pm 0.074 \times 10^6$ cells/µL, respectively. The average amount of haemoglobin was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) in people with polycythaemia who did not smoke and in people who did smoke compared to healthy people. It was 17.00 ± 4.218 , 17.36 ± 0.112 , and 14.67 ± 0.186 g/dl, respectively. The results of the research coincide with the findings of the researcher [12], where the researcher attributed the reason for the decline in the percentage of hemoglobin to a decrease in the antioxidant rates of both glutathione and the effectiveness of the enzyme glutathium peroxidase in

red blood cells in smoking patients, which is one of the reasons for the increase in the breakdown of red cells. The researcher [7] found that one of the extreme effects of exposing vital tissues, including red cells, to cigarette smoke is a decrease in the levels of glutathione, which indicates its effect on these cells and exposing them to damage associated with the formation of free radicals by iron, which increases due to exposure to high concentrations of cigarette smoke. Scientists found [8] that the number of red blood cells increases in smokers, and the percentage of blood separation (HCT) begins to decrease after cessation of smoking. Scientists have attributed the high number of red blood cells to the decrease in oxygenation of body tissues, which leads to an increase in the proportion of carboxy Hb and an increase in the secretion of the hormone EPO from the kidneys, meaning that the high number of red blood cells is a kind of normalization method for lack of oxygen caused by the high

percentage of carbon monoxide CO. High red blood cell counts in smokers increase the likelihood of errors during DNA repair due to stimulation of bone marrow cell division [9]. The results showed a significant increase at the level of probability ($P < 0.001$) in the percentage of blood separation, as its levels reached (54.51 ± 0.454 , 54.39 ± 0.319 , 46.39 ± 0.433) for non-smokers, smokers and healthy people respectively. While the average blood cell size (MCV), mean hemoglobin (MCH) and average hemoglobin concentration (MCHC) showed no significant differences between patients and healthy people, except for the ratio of red cell proliferation capacity, which indicated a significant increase at the level of probability ($P < 0.05$) between the groups of patients and healthy people. The statistical analysis also showed no significant differences between the mean red cell parameters in the group of polycythemia patients compared to non-smoking patients ($P < 0.05$).

Table 1: Red Blood Cell Criteria for Patients with Polycythemia (Non-Smokers and Smokers) Compared to Healthy Individuals

Standard Number	Control 40	Non-smoking polycythemia patients 36	Patients with polycythemia Smoking 54
Age (years)	1.095 ±31.10	2.313±45.02***	1.781±40.81***
Red blood cell count 10^6 (cell/ μ L)	0.075±5.21	0.064±6.00***	0.074±5.95***
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	0.186±14.67	4.218±17.00*	0.112±17.36*
Separated Blood %	0.433±46.39	0.454±54.51***	0.319±54.39***
Average pellet size (fl)	1.223±89.27	0.825±90.80	0.814±91.76
Average hemoglobin (g/dL)	0.512±28.30	0.338±28.65	0.386±29.37
Average concentration of hemoglobin (g/dL)	0.211±31.63	0.203±31.52	0.178±31.91
Erythropia Spread Capacity %	0.288±12.30	0.237±13.13*	0.244±13.17*

Table (2) shows the average number of white blood cells in people with polycythaemia who smoke and people who don't smoke compared to healthy people. The number of total white blood cells in people with polycythaemia who smoke and people who don't smoke compared to healthy people went up significantly ($p < 0.05$), reaching 9.55 ± 0.696 , 8.52 ± 0.484 , and 9.08 ± 1.046 cells/microliter, respectively. The number of lymphocytes in non-smoking polycythaemia patients is significantly lower than in healthy people ($p = 0.001$); they were found to be (2.05 ± 0.156) 103 cells/microliter compared to 2.66 ± 0.099 for healthy people. The table shows a significant increase at the level of probability ($p < 0.05$) in mononuclear cells in patients with polycythemia smokers compared to non-smokers and healthy people, as it reached (0.75 ± 0.040 , 0.60 ± 0.051 , 0.60 ± 0.056) 103 cells/microliter respectively. Statisticians looked at the rates of eosinophils, basophils, and platelets in the blood of smokers with polycythaemia, nonsmokers, and healthy

people. They found no significant changes ($p > 0.05$) between the groups.

The present study found that the average numbers of white blood cells (neutrophils, monocytes, eosinophils, and basophils) went up by a large amount ($p < 0.001$). One more thing that this study found is that the number of lymphocytes in a group of people with polycythaemia dropped significantly ($p < 0.001$). Neutrophils are more common in smokers' blood because, in addition to fighting germs, they damage tissue and cause inflammation outside of cells. It also shows that people with polycythaemia, both smokers and nonsmokers, have a lot more neutrophils than healthy people. This means that more effective oxygen radicals are being made, which infects vascular epithelial cells and changes how they regulate things like blood clotting. The active oxygen types of free radicals are generated by neutrophils from various sources such as Mitochondrial Xanthine Oxidase enzymes, NADPH Oxidase, so it is the main source of active roots in the blood, which have physiological

effects on the reproduction of bone marrow Myeloproliferation, and the hydrogen peroxide H₂O₂ produced can affect different cells and tissues such as vascular epithelial cells, leading to an increase in the secretion of Von Willebrand Factor, which is the main factor in the external coagulation pathway (Extrinsic blood coagulation). pathway) [10] noted that myelopropagation is associated with blood thrombosis

formation and vascular complications and that its pathogenicity is not fully known, but active oxygen radicals produced by the enzyme NADPH oxidase for neutrophils have a role in this process. The reason for the decrease in lymphocyte counts in smokers is due to the impact of smoking on cellular immunity and the mixed immune response by stopping lymphocyte proliferation and stimulating their self-destruction [11].

Table 2: Criteria of white Blood Cells for Polycythemia Patients (Non-Smokers and Smokers) Compared to Healthy People

Standard Number	Control 40	Non-smoking polycythemia patients 36	Patients with polycythemia Smoking 54
Blood white cell count 10 ³ (cell/microL)	0.484±8.52	1.046 ±9.08 *	0.696±9.55*
Neutrophils 10 ³ (cell/microL)	0.252±5.06	0.798±6.14	0.415±5.88
Lymphocytes 10 ³ (cell/microL)	0.099±2.66	0.156±2.05***	0.217±2.65
Monocytes 10 ³ (cell/microliter)	0.056±0.60	0.051±0.60	0.040±0.75*
Eosinophils 10 ³ (cell/microL)	0.025±0.18	0.031±0.20	0.018±0.19
Basophils 10 ³ (cell/microL)	0.052±0.02	0.010±0.09	0.006±0.08
Platelets 10 ³ (Plate/μL)	8.808±277.37	19.612±286.55	11.148±271.48

Conclusion

It is clear that smoking has an impact on the blood values of people with polycythaemia. The study found that smokers had significantly higher numbers of red blood cells and haematocrit. They also had significantly higher numbers of white blood cells and lower numbers of neutrophils, monocytes, and other types of white blood cells. Compared to people who don't smoke, the average amount of lymphocytes and basophils also dropped by a lot.

References

[1] Siamak T, Nabii MD. International conference on residency education. *Am J Med.* 2013;34:554-8.
 [2] Ang SO, Chen H, Hirota K, et al. Disruption of oxygen homeostasis underlies congenital Chuvash polycythemia. *Nat Genet.* 2002;32:614-21. doi: 10.1038/ng1047.
 [3] Gale DP, Harten SK, Reid CD, Tuddenham EG, Maxwell PH. Autosomal dominant erythrocytosis and pulmonary arterial hypertension associated with an activating HIF2 alpha mutation. *Blood.* 2008;112:919-21. doi: 10.1182/blood-2007-10-118273
 [4] Gönenç A, Atak Y, Orman MN, Simsek B. Lipid peroxidation and antioxidant systems in hemodialyzed patients: dialysis and transplantation. *J Biomed Sci.* 2002;31(2):135-40. doi: 10.1146/annurev.biochem.71.110601.135549

[5] Cheng ZY, Li ZY. What is responsible for the initiating chemistry of iron-mediated lipid peroxidation? An update. *Chem Rev.* 2007;3:748-66. doi: 10.1021/cr068326e
 [6] Sysmex Corporation. Sysmex KX-21N Operator's Manual. Kobe, Japan: Sysmex Corporation; 1999.
 [7] Mehlhorn RJ. Increased vulnerability of human erythrocytes to hydroperoxide damage after exposure to cigarette smoke or 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene in vitro. *Nicotine Tob Res.* 2000;2:141-8. doi: 10.1080/14622200050147482
 [8] Van TE, Peeters PHM, Smit HA. Quitting smoking may restore hematologic characteristics within five years. *Ann Epidemiol.* 2002;12:378-88. doi: 10.1016/S1047-2797(02)00306-7
 [9] Branzei D, Foiani M. Regulation of DNA repair throughout the cell cycle. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol.* 2008;9:297-308. doi: 10.1038/nrm2351
 [10] Nedelec M, McCall A, Carling C, Legall F, Berthoin S, Dupont G. The influence of soccer playing actions on the recovery kinetics after a soccer match. *Am J Sports Med.* 2013;34:554-8. doi: 10.1177/0363546514558142

[11] El-Zayadi A. Heavy smoking and liver. *J Gastroenterol Hepatol.* 2006;12:6098-102. doi: 10.3748/wjg.v12.i38.6101

[12] Codandabany U. Erythrocyte lipid peroxidation in cigarette smokers. *Cell Biochem.* 2000;18:99-102. doi: 10.1002/(SICI)1099-0844(199601/02)18:1<99::AID-PSC200>3.0.CO;2-N.

